

Electronic Effects of Substituted Aromatic Ring on the Methanogenic Toxicity

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ABSTRACT

A study of the substituents electronic effects on the methanogenic toxicity of aromatic compounds was realized at room temperature using the standard method of serum bottles. The pig digested manure and sodium acetate (pH 7) were used as inoculum and substrate, respectively. The toxicity on the acetoclastic methanogens (archaea) was determined by measuring the methane gas volume produced by serum bottles liquid displacement system (Mariotte flask system). The obtained results indicate a correlation between the nature of the substituents on the aromatic ring and their inhibitory effects on the biosynthesis of the methane gas by the acetoclastic methanogenic bacteria. Of the 13 studied compounds, Nitrobenzene and Phloroglucinol, with IC_{50} values of 3.92 and 3151.49 mg/L, respectively, were the most and the least toxic compounds.

Keywords: methanogenic toxicity, inhibition, biogaz, benzene, methanogenic bacteria, biomethanization, methane.

INTRODUCTION

The shortage of traditional fossil fuels makes the search for alternative and sustainable energy sources a necessity. Biogaz production through methanization constitutes one approach to security and diversification of energy production. In addition, the methanization treatment of industrial effluents and agricultural organic wastes is efficient in slowing down the environment pollution, deforestation and global warming. [1-4]

However, during the anaerobic treatment of industrial effluents and waste, aromatic compounds have been found to be toxic to methanogenic bacteria, hence limiting the biomethanization processes. [4,5]

In a previous study, Kayembe *et al.* [4] have studied the inhibition effects of phenolic monomers, and found that the limitation of the biomethanization processes was dependent on the nature and concentration of the aromatic compounds.

As part of our continued interest in the effects of aromatic compounds on the methanogenic toxicity, we undertook the investigation of the electronic effects of variously substituted aromatic compounds. In fact, it is important to understand the influence of substituents on the aromatic ring towards methanogenic toxicity in order to prevent their inhibitory effects during the anaerobic digestion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Biomass

Pig manure from Domaine Agro-Industriel de la N'sele (DAIPN)/Kinshasa (DR Congo) was digested in laboratory scale digester for about six months. The digested pig manure (sludge), not previously acclimated to any aromatic compounds, was utilized as inoculums in anaerobic toxicity tests.

The characteristics of inoculums were: total suspended solids (TSS, 91.10g/L), volatile suspended matter (VSM, 56.59g/L), and specific acetoclastic methanogenic activity: 163.40-210.81mg COD-CH₄/g VSS.d (27±1°C).

Stock Solutions

Stock substrate solution

The stock solution of the substrate consisted of a solution of sodium acetate (pH=7) obtained by reacting acetic acid with NaOH. A concentration of 100g COD-CH₃COOH/L (chemical oxygen demand per liter) was used in this study.

Stock solution 1

NH₄Cl (170g/L), KH₂PO₄ (37g/L), MgSO₄.4H₂O (37g/L), and CaCl₂.2H₂O (10 g/L). [1,4]

Stock solution 2

FeCl₃.4H₂O (200 mg/L), CoCl₂.6H₂O (2000 mg/L), MnCl₂.4H₂O (50 mg/L), CuCl₂.2H₂O (50 mg/L), ZnCl₂ (50 mg/L), H₃BO₃ (50 mg/L), (NH₄)₃MO₇O₂.4H₂O (90 mg/L), Na₂SeO₃.5H₂O (100 mg/L), EDTA (1000 mg/L), HCl 36% (1mg/l), NiCl₂.6H₂O (50 mg/L), yeast extract (200 mg/L), and resazurin (500mg/L). [1,4]

Aromatic Compounds

Twelve (12) aromatic compounds with both electron donating and electron withdrawing groups were used. These are Phenol, Aniline, Nitrobenzene, Chlorobenzene, Catechol, Hydroquinone, p-Aminophenol, p-Nitrophenol, p-Nitroaniline, Phloroglucinol, Pyrogallol and Resorcinol. Benzene was used as reference for comparison purposes, making a total of 13 compounds studied.

Anaerobic Toxicity Assay

Specific acetoclastic methanogenic activity measurements were performed with 1L glass serum bottles sealed with rubber septa. These measurements were done based on the following procedure: Add to each serum bottle from the digester 1.5 g VSM of digested pig manure, 2 mL stock solution 1, 1 mL stock solution 2 and 40 mL stock substrate solution. Fill the serum bottle to about 1000 mL with oxygen free tap water (tap water flushed with nitrogen gas for at least 15 minutes). [1,4,6] Seal the flask with rubber septum cap and shake it at room temperature for a few minutes.

The required quantity of test compounds (toxicants) was added to provide the concentrations to be investigated. No toxicant was added to the controls. The toxicant concentrations were chosen as

to induce an inhibition (0-100%) of the acetoclastic methanogenic activity. [1,4,7,8] The concentrations of inhibitors used in the anaerobic toxicity assay are given in the table 1.

The specific methanogenic activity was calculated from the slope of the cumulative methane production versus time curve and the

quantity of VSM. The compound concentration that caused 50% inhibition of the methanogenic activities of the control and samples containing inhibitory compounds were determined. [1,4,9,10]

Table 1. The inhibitory concentration of compounds used in anaerobic toxicity assay

N°	Aromatic Compounds	Concentrations (mg/L)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Benzene	0	150	300	450	600
2	Phenol	0	500	700	1500	3000
3	Aniline	0	500	700	1500	3000
4	Nitrobenzene	0	2	3	6	9
5	Chlorobenzene	0	10	15	30	50
6	Catechol	0	1000	2500	3500	4500
7	Hydroquinone	0	1000	2500	3500	4500
8	Resorcinol	0	1000	2500	3500	4500
9	p-Aminophenol	0	1000	2000	3000	4000
10	p-Nitrophenol	0	15	20	40	60
11	p-Nitroaniline	0	15	20	40	60
12	Phloroglucinol	0	1500	3500	4500	6000
13	Pyrogallol	0	1500	3500	4500	6000

Methane Gas Measurement

The volume of methane gas produced was measured by serum bottle liquid displacement systems (Mariotte flask system) as previously described [4,5,8,10]. The liquid used was a solution of NaOH (15 mg/L). As the biogas passes through these high pH solutions, the CO₂ of biogas is converted to carbonate and absorbed into the liquid. Only methane gas passes through the solution and an equivalent volume is pushed out of the mariotte flask. The volume of the displaced liquid is then measured in a graduated cylinder. [4-6]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Inhibition of Specific Methanogenic Activity

The inhibitory effect of the test compounds and the reference (Benzene) on the activity of acetoclastic methanogenic bacteria was studied at different concentrations ranging from 2-6000 mg/L. This is exemplified by the experiment with p-Aminophenol as shown in figure 1 below, from which the the IC₅₀ was calculated as the concentration of p-Aminophenol corresponding to 50% of inhibition.

The method used to calculate the IC₅₀ is illustrated in this figure was extended to all test compounds.

Figure 1. Methanogenic activity of digested pig manure exposed to p-Aminophenol as a function of Aminophenol concentration.

Table 2 below summarizes the inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) and the partition coefficient of test compounds. Partition coefficient taken in n-Octanol/water system. [11]

Table 2. Inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) and the partition coefficient values of the test compounds.

Test Compounds	Inhibitory Concentrations(IC ₅₀)	Log P _{oct.}
Nitrobenzene	3.92	1.85
Chlorobenzene	32.25	3.35
p-Nitrophenol	40.82	1.91
p-Nitroaniline	44.74	1.27
Benzene	170.22	2.13
Phenol	966.27	1.47
Aniline	1038.74	0.90
Catechol	1436.28	0.88
p-Aminophenol	1721.35	0.80
Resorcinol	2014.90	0.104
Hydroquinone	2760.00	0.59
Pyrogallol	2826.55	0.97
Phloroglucinol	3151.49	0.16

Electronic Effect of Substituents on the Methanogenic Toxicity

The mechanism of action of aromatic compounds on the methanogenic toxicity had been explained by their absorption on the cellular membrane of methanogenic bacteria and the modification of cellular diffusion that can lead to superficial tension change. [5,12] However, recently [12], it has been reported that this mechanism of action could also be explained by the disturbance of interactions between Coenzyme M (within the methanogenic bacteria) and the acetate substrate (from the decomposition of organic matter). [12] The interactions are established by the formation of a complex between Coenzyme M and acetate substrate, leading to the production of methane. This involves charge transfer between Coenzyme M and the aromatic ring.

In fact, the disruption of interactions between Coenzyme M and the acetate substrate is known to be greatly dependent on the nature (electron donating groups, electron withdrawing groups, or both) of the substituents on the aromatic ring. [12]

Effects of the electron withdrawing groups (EWGs)

Compared to Benzene, EWGs make the aromatic compounds more toxic towards methanogenic bacteria. During this investigation, Nitro group was found to be more toxic than the Chloro group (table 3). This is explained by both its pronounced inductive effect and its reactive nature towards the cellular components of the bacteria.

Table 3. IC₅₀ values and electronic parameters of Benzene, Chlorobenzene and Nitrobenzene.

R	Compound	IC ₅₀ (mg/L)	σ	φ
R= H	Benzene	170.22	0	0
R= Cl	Chlorobenzene	32.25	0.28	0
R= NO ₂	Nitrobenzene	3.92	0.60	0

σ and φ are Hammett parameters representing the inductive strength (withdrawing power) and the sensitivity of donor, respectively. [13]

In fact, the substitution of -NO₂ for -H (on the Benzene ring) stabilizes the negative charge on the ring, and hence the Coenzyme M-Aromatic ring complex, in lieu of favoring/stabilizing the interactions between Coenzyme M and the acetate substrate.

This is confirmed by both the IC₅₀ values and Hammett parameters (σ, φ) as shown in table 3, in which Nitrobenzene was found to be more toxic (IC₅₀=3.92 mg/L) than Chlorobenzene (IC₅₀=32.25 mg/L) and Benzene (IC₅₀=170.22 mg/L).

Effects of electron donating groups (EDGs)

Likewise, Phenol and Aniline (two EDGs bearing aromatic compounds) were studied and were found to be less toxic than Benzene (table 4).

Table 4. IC₅₀ values and electronic parameters of Benzene, Phenol and Aniline.

R	Compound	IC ₅₀ (mg/L)	σ	φ
R= H	Benzene	170.22	0	0
R= OH	Phenol	966.27	0	1.06
R= NH ₂	Aniline	1038.74	0	1.08

σ and φ are Hammett parameters .

The presence of EDGs on the aromatic ring slows (hydrophilic nature of the -OH and -NH₂ groups) its penetration of the cellular membrane by destabilizing the Coenzyme M-Aromatic ring complex, hence favoring the methylation of Coenzyme M by the acetate substrate. [12]

In fact, Aniline was found to be less toxic than Phenol due to the pronounced electron donating nature of the amino group (-NH₂) over -OH.

Groups having additive or opposed effects

Aromatic compounds bearing substituents of additive or opposed inductive nature (p-Aminophenol, p-Nitroaniline and p-Nitrophenol) were also investigated in this study and displayed a variability towards methanogenic toxicity (table 5).

Table 5. IC₅₀ values of Benzene, p-Aminophenol, p-Nitroaniline and p-Nitrophenol.

R	Compound	IC ₅₀ (mg/L)
R ¹ = R ² = H	Benzene	170.22
R ¹ =OH, R ² = NO ₂	p-Nitrophenol	40.82
R ¹ = NH ₂ , R ² = NO ₂	p-Nitroaniline	44.74
R ¹ =NH ₂ , R ² = OH	p-Aminophenol	1721.35

p-Aminophenol (bearing two electron donating groups) was found to be the least toxic compound (IC₅₀=1721.35 mg/L) towards methanogenic bacteria. This is explained by the additive effects of the Amino and Hydroxyl groups that increase the electronic density on the Benzene ring and hence destabilizing the Coenzyme M-Aromatic ring complex more than the individual Aniline and Phenol (IC₅₀=1038.74 mg/L and IC₅₀=966.27 mg/L, respectively).

The next less toxic compound towards methanogenic bacteria was p-Nitroaniline (IC₅₀=44.74 mg/L). Compared to Aniline, the increased toxicity of this compound can be explained by the presence of a Nitro group on the Benzene ring. By its negative inductive effect, -NO₂ stabilizes the negative charge on the ring, making the methylation of Coenzyme M by the acetate substrate difficult because its complex with the aromatic ring is more stabilized by the electron withdrawing groups.

Finally, and as expected, p-Nitrophenol was found to be the most toxic compound. This is due to the electron donating effect of -OH group which is weaker, compared to that of the Amino group. Benzene was used for comparison purposes throughout this study.

Effects of the number and position of electron donating groups on the aromatic ring

In order to expand the applicability of our approach and in comparison with Benzene and Phenol, a few compounds bearing two or three -OH groups viz: Catechol, Resorcinol, Hydroquinone, Pyrogallol and Phloroglucinol, were also investigated for their inhibitory effect on the activity of acetoclastic bacteria towards methanogenesis.

Table 6. IC₅₀ values of Benzene, Phenol, Catechol, Resorcinol, Hydroquinone, Pyrogallol and Phloroglucinol.

R	Compound	IC ₅₀ (mg/L)
R ¹ =R ² =R ³ =R ⁴ =H	Benzene	170.22
R ¹ =OH, R ² =R ³ =R ⁴ =H	Phenol	966.27
R ¹ =R ² =OH, R ³ =R ⁴ =H	Catechol	1436.28
R ¹ =R ³ =OH, R ² =R ⁴ =H	Resorcinol	2014.90
R ² =R ⁴ =OH, R ¹ =R ³ =H	Hydroquinone	2760.00
R ¹ =R ² =R ³ =OH, R ⁴ =H	Pyrogallol	2826.55
R ¹ =R ³ =R ⁴ =OH, R ² =H	Phloroglucinol	3151.49

As already stated, the electron donating character of hydroxyl group destabilizes the Coenzyme M-Benzene ring complex. This and the hydrophilic nature of the –OH group (that make it difficult for the aromatic compound to be transported through the lipidic bacteria membranes and establish a complex with the bacteria Coenzyme M) facilitate the methylation of Coenzyme M by the acetate substrate, leading to the production of methane gas.

The more the number of –OH groups on the Benzene ring, the less toxic is that compound towards the methanogenic bacteria. Thus, the observed toxicity for the investigated compounds followed the order Benzene > Phenol > Catechol > Resorcinol > Hydroquinone > Pyrogallol > Phloroglucinol.

In addition, the position of –OH groups on the Benzene ring had an influence on the toxicity of the compound towards methanogenic bacteria.

For example, Catechol (1,2-dihydroxybenzene) was found to be more toxic than Resorcinol (1,3-dihydroxybenzene) and Hydroquinone (1,4-dihydroxybenzene), and this is explained by the ortho relationship between the two groups of Catechol that are close enough to form an intramolecular hydrogen bond that make the compound more hydrophobic. The hydrophobic nature of a compound facilitates its transportation through lipidic bacteria membranes, hence complexing the Coenzyme M. Resorcinol was also found to be more toxic than Hydroquinone (IC₅₀=2014.90 mg/L and IC₅₀=2760.00 mg/L, respectively).

Likewise, this trend was also observed for compounds bearing three –OH groups in which Pyrogallol (1,2,3-trihydroxybenzene) was found to be more toxic towards methanogenic bacteria than Phloroglucinol (1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene). Their observed IC₅₀ values were 2826.55 mg/L and 3151.49 mg/L, respectively.

NB: Nitrobenzene, CB: Chlorobenzene, p-NB: p-Nitrobenzene, p-NA: p-Nitroaniline, B: Benzene, P: Phenol, A: Aniline, C: Catechol, p-AP: p-Aminophenol, R: Resorcinol, H: Hydroquinone, Py: Pyrogallol, and Ph: Phloroglucinol.

Figure 2. Effect of the nature of aromatic compounds on Methanogenic toxicity

CONCLUSION

This study aimed at exploring the electronic effects of substituted aromatic ring on the Methanogenic toxicity.

Our results indicate a correlation between the nature (number and position) of both the electron donating and electron withdrawing groups on Benzene ring and its toxicity towards methanogenic bacteria.

In general, compounds with electron withdrawing groups were found to be more toxic towards methanogenic bacteria than those having electron donating groups. In addition, compounds having an increased number of substituents showed an additive or opposing effect, depending on whether the substituents were of the same nature (electron donating) or opposed nature (electron donating and electron withdrawing).

Moreover, compounds bearing substituents close enough to form intramolecular H-bonds are more hydrophobic (more lipophilic) and hence more toxic.

From the observed behavior, we can anticipate that compounds having substituents of the same but electron withdrawing nature should also have additive effect and become even more toxic than their singly-substituted representatives such as chlorobenzene and nitrobenzene.

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